

AN ANALOGOUS INVESTIGATION ON TRANSVERSE CRACKING IN COMPOSITE LAMINATE AND CONCRETE PAVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Based on experimental study of transverse cracking in graphite-epoxy laminates under tensile loading, a three-stage mode for crack growth correlated to random defects is presented. A general plane cracking model associated with the interlaminar stresses is developed to predict the saturate crack density, stiffness loss and growth of crack density, and gives good agreement with experimental results. Study shows the saturate crack density will increase greatly while the final stiffness loss keeps constant if the thickness of individual 90° plies is reduced under the same content of total 90° plies in laminate. Reasonable description of the FPF and stiffness degradation of a lamina shows they strongly correlate to the adjacent plies. A formula of stiffness loss due to edge delamination and transverse crack is concluded by means of a parallel springs model and compared with the experimental data of GFRP laminates. The modified form of strain energy release rate of edge delamination is also presented. Shear-lag analysis of the two-layer system in asphalt concrete pavement is used to explain the regular cracking state. The predicted saturate transverse cracks spacing comes from the solution of a stress function and it approaches the measured value.

KEYWORDS: Composite Laminate; Concrete Pavement; Transverse Cracking; Saturate Crack Spacing (Density).

1. INTRODUCTION

Transverse (matrix) cracking is a main failure mode of fibrous lamina and the sign of damage development in composites laminate. It often occurs under static and cyclic tensile loading, cyclic temperature loading and impact loading etc. It will cause stresses redistribution then induce local delamination, fiber breaking and other damages [1-5]. Since the practical laminate often bears the multi-directional loading, the 90° plies become necessary in laminate. The transverse cracking in 90° plies attracts a lot of researchers [6-14]. Transverse cracking in concrete pavement is a worldwide problem. It has great effect on the durability and maintainance cost of the highway, further research on mechanism and modeling should be explored. However, concrete is a kind of particle reinforced composite, concrete pavement is a laminated structure [15-16], the transverse cracking both in composite laminate and concrete pavement will form a regular crack spacing state [16]. So an analogous study on transverse cracking will become a valuable routine.

2. EXPERIMENT AND OBSERVATION

The unnotched graphite-epoxy specimens are T300/648, $[0_2/90_3]_S$ and T300/Ag80, $[0/90_n/0]_T$, $[45/90_n/0/-45]_S$, $n=1, 2, 3$. All the tests were conducted at a MTS 880 machine. Specimens under quasi-static loading were measured their crack densities and stiffness loss at every given applied tensile strain. Tension-tension fatigue test on $[0_2/90_3]_S$ laminate was measured the same damage parameters at a given load cycle. ($R=0.01$, $f=10\text{Hz}$) Crack growth was detected by edge replication and x-ray radiograph [1, 16]. Replica tape was put into a slide projector to show the in-situ crack details, or was

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used to be the negative directly to develop photoes.

By the examination of optical microscope, two types of microvoids were found in the edge surface of 90° plies in $[0_2/90_3]_S$ laminate. One type of microvoids was bigger and fewer and in oblate shape, it's inferred to be caused by the air in plies which couldn't escape in time during curing process. The microvoids in globe shape were mainly caused by the action of the volatile component in epoxy. Most of the globe microvoids become the origins of transverse cracks but the oblate microvoids rarely have transverse cracks to occur. (See Fig.1) This phenomenon could be included in Wang's "effective flaws" assumption that transverse cracks stem from a Weibull distribution of flaws representing all the defects in 90° plies [3]. Typical experimental curves of crack growth were illustrated in Fig.2. The development of transverse crack could be divided into three stages associated with the effective flaws assumption. The first FPF stage is associated with the onset of transverse crack formed by the longest flaw a_{max} , so the crack density increases slowly because of the fewer number of a_{max} . Subsequently, the crack density will come into a rapid increase stage which is corresponding to a number of microflaws to form transverse cracks possibly. During the last CDS stage, according to the feature of probability density function, the flaws in short length are fewer, so the crack density increases slowly and seems to tend to a limit value. However, the crack density will be believed to increase even very slowly unless the catastrophic failure of the laminate occurs. Whatever in quasi-static or cyclic tensile tests, the same trend can be seen [2-4]. It should be noted that in fatigue test the three-stage curve will be destroyed by the σ_{max} and the catastrophic failure of the laminate. In our test, longitudinal split and local delamination were observed only in $[0_2/90_3]_S$ laminate under fatigue loading.

3. TRANSVERSE CRACKING IN COMPOSITE LAMINATE

3.1 Cracking in the Laminate with Central 90° Plies Consider a cross-ply laminate under applied tensile loading σ_a shown in Fig.1. According to experimental observation, the longitudinal displacement across the cracked 90° plies is assumed to be

$$U_{90} = f(x)y^a + g(x) \quad (1)$$

The equilibrium conditions for the entire laminate and the 0° plies require

$$(t_e + t_{90})\sigma_a = t_e \sigma_e + t_{90} \bar{\sigma}_{90} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{d\sigma_e}{dx} = \frac{\tau_{90}(x, t_{90})}{t_e} \quad (3)$$

where subscripts e and 90 represent 0° and 90° plies. And the total stress σ in x direction is the sum of mechanical stress σ^M and residual stress σ^R . But the residual stresses are in self-equilibrium. By means of the displacement continuity condition and the approximate linear stress-strain relationships, the average mechanical stress in 90° plies $\bar{\sigma}_{90}^M$ and 0° plies σ_e^M are obtained

$$\bar{\sigma}_{90}^M = \frac{E_{90}}{E_x} \sigma_a - \frac{t_e}{t_{90}} (C_1 e^{-kx} + C_2 e^{kx}) \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_e^M = C_1 e^{-kx} + C_2 e^{kx} + \frac{E_e}{E_x} \sigma_a \quad (5)$$

where E_x^0 is the longitudinal modulus of the laminate without transverse cracks and K is the shear-lag constant

$$K^2 = \frac{(\alpha + 1)G(E_e t_e + E_{90} t_{90})}{E_{90} E_e t_{90} t_e} \quad (6)$$

where G should be the interlaminar shear modulus G_{23} . Generally, it's assumed equal to the intralaminar shear modulus G_{12} . When FPF occurs in the laminate, the boundary conditions are

$$\sigma_\varepsilon = \frac{t_\varepsilon + t_{90}}{t_\varepsilon} \sigma_a \quad (x=0), \quad \tau_{90}(x, t_{90}) = \frac{d\sigma_\varepsilon^M}{dx} = 0 \quad (x \rightarrow \infty) \quad (7)$$

then

$$\bar{\sigma}_{90} = \left(\frac{E_{90}}{E_x^0} \sigma_a + \sigma_{90}^R \right) (1 - e^{-kx}) \quad (8)$$

When there are several cracks with an average spacing $2L$, (crack density $D = 1/2L$) the boundary conditions are given by

$$\bar{\sigma}_{90} = 0 \quad (x = \pm L), \quad \tau_{90} = 0 \quad (x = 0) \quad (9)$$

Equation (8) is replaced by

$$\bar{\sigma}_{90} = \left(\frac{E_{90}}{E_x^0} \sigma_a + \sigma_{90}^R \right) \left(1 - \frac{\cosh(KX)}{\cosh(KL)} \right) \quad (10)$$

When the central 90° plies are cracked, the average strain of the laminate will be reflected by the adjacent plies not the mid-plane plies. It becomes

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{\sigma_a}{E_x^0} \left(1 + \frac{E_{90} t_{90} 2D}{E_\varepsilon t_\varepsilon K} \operatorname{tanh}\left(\frac{K}{2D}\right) \right) + \frac{t_{90} \sigma_{90}^R 2D}{t_\varepsilon E_\varepsilon K} \operatorname{tanh}\left(\frac{K}{2D}\right) \quad (11)$$

In practical computation, the strain induced by the residual stress is found small and can be neglected. If the longitudinal modulus of the damaged laminate E_x is expressed by the secant modulus, then

$$E_x / E_x^0 = \left(1 + \frac{E_{90} t_{90} 2D}{E_\varepsilon t_\varepsilon K} \operatorname{tanh}\left(\frac{K}{2D}\right) \right)^{-1} \quad (12)$$

When the first transverse crack occurs in the most serious defect, a shear-lag region will form in the cracked plies [3, 8]. Other defects form the transverse cracks outside this region due to the higher tensile stress. Only at higher applied loading or a number of load cycles, those defects inside shear-lag region are possible to form transverse cracks. From the viewpoint of statistics, the half length of shear-lag region can be regarded to be the saturate crack spacing L_{CDS} , i.e., from eqn (8)

$$1 - e^{-KL_{CDS}} = 1 - \varepsilon, \quad \varepsilon \leq 0.1 \quad (13)$$

For those laminates with serious defects, ε should be given a big value. But for the same materials under same curing process, ε should be a constant for all laminates. The experimental curves of stress-strain and crack development are shown in Fig.3. When the crack density D increase to $D + \Delta D$, the energy relationship is given by

$$\Delta W - \Delta U = 4l \cdot t_{90} \cdot v_F \cdot \Delta D \quad (14)$$

where ΔW is the work done by the applied load, ΔU is the increase of strain energy and v_F is the surface fracture energy density.

$$\Delta W = 2(t_\varepsilon + t_{90}) \cdot l \cdot \frac{1}{2} (\sigma_a + \sigma_a + \Delta\sigma_a) \cdot \Delta\varepsilon_x \quad (15)$$

The difficulty is the precise description of ΔU . According to experimental observation, the damaged laminate also shows linear stress-strain relation with a small residual strain $\bar{\varepsilon}_x^R$. (when $\sigma_a = 0$). Thus ΔU could be written by

$$\Delta U = -2(t_\varepsilon + t_{90}) \cdot l \cdot \left[\frac{1}{2} \sigma_a (\varepsilon_x - \bar{\varepsilon}_{x1}^R) - \frac{1}{2} (\sigma_a + \Delta\sigma_a) \cdot (\varepsilon_x + \Delta\varepsilon_x - \bar{\varepsilon}_{x2}^R) \right] \quad (16)$$

Hence, the recurrence relation between applied loading and crack density can be established. In experiment, only the crack growth under fixed loading was observed, $\bar{\varepsilon}_{x1}^R$ approaches $\bar{\varepsilon}_{x2}^R$ and both of them are very small. In order to simplify the calculation, we assume $\Delta\sigma_a = 0$ and neglect $\bar{\varepsilon}_{x1}^R$, $\bar{\varepsilon}_{x2}^R$, then

$$\sigma_a = \frac{1}{2} \left(-\frac{E_x^0}{E_{90}^0} \sigma_{90}^R + \sqrt{\left(\frac{E_x^0}{E_{90}^0} \sigma_{90}^R\right)^2 + 4 \left(\frac{2v_{ft} t_e E_e K E_x^0}{(t_e + t_{90}) E_{90}^0}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{2(D + \Delta D) \text{tanh}\left(\frac{K}{2(D + \Delta D)}\right) - 2D \text{tanh}\left(\frac{K}{2D}\right)}{\Delta D}\right)} \right) \quad (17)$$

But $\Delta D = f(\sigma_a) \cdot D$, it should be calculated according to the three-stage mode. Considering the new crack is more possible to form in the middle of two existing cracks from the stress analysis, we simply assume $\Delta D = 1.0D$, then

$$\sigma_a = \frac{1}{2} \left(-\frac{E_x^0}{E_{90}^0} \sigma_{90}^R + \sqrt{\left(\frac{E_x^0}{E_{90}^0} \sigma_{90}^R\right)^2 + 4 \left(\frac{2v_{ft} t_e E_e K E_x^0}{(t_e + t_{90}) E_{90}^0}\right) \left(2 \text{tanh}\left(\frac{K}{4D}\right) - \text{tanh}\left(\frac{K}{2D}\right)\right)} \right) \quad (18)$$

The progressive failure of the 90° plies can be expressed by its stiffness degradation. We definite R_1, R_2 as the degradation factors of stiffness of 90° plies in longitudinal and transverse directions respectively. They are written by

$$R_2 = 1 - \frac{2D}{K} \text{tanh}\left(\frac{K}{2D}\right) \quad (19)$$

$$R_1 = 1 - (1 - R_2) \frac{V_m E_m}{E_1} \quad (20)$$

Eqn.(19) tallies with eqn.(12). When the transverse crack spacing increases to the magnitude of the diameter of fiber or so, $R_2 \approx 0$, and R_1 will be given the value derived from the stiffness rule of mixtures $E_1 = E_m V_m + E_f V_f$ [18]. Clearly, K , which is correlated strongly to the characteristic of adjacent plies, plays an important role in the progressive intralaminar failure in laminate.

3.2. The Influence of Changing Layup If the central plies are divided into two parts with central and outside 0° plies, for instance, $[0_2/90]_S$ is replaced by $[0/90/0]_S$. By means of shear-lag analysis, the stiffness loss due to transverse cracks can be also expressed by eqn(12). However, the shear-lag constant will be rewritten by[16]

$$K^2 = \frac{(\alpha + 1)G(E_c t_c + E_s t_s + E_{90} t_{90})}{E_{90} t_{90}^2 (E_c t_c + E_s t_s)} \quad (21)$$

i.e., $E_e \cdot t_e$ in eqn(6) is replaced by $E_c t_c + E_s t_s$ in eqn(21). It should be noted that the thickness of total 90° plies in the the case for eqn(6) is $2t_{90}$ but in the case for eqn(21) is $4t_{90}$. If the 90° plies are surface plies of the laminate, for instance, $[0/90]_S$ is changed to $[90/0]_S$, the same results are found as in last chapter. However, experiment showed different crack growth and final CDS state existed in $[0/90]_S$ and $[90/0]_S$ laminates[4]. Because different distribution of the interlaminar stresses exist in two types of laminates and the shear-lag constant represents mainly the result of interlaminar shear stress. α in eqn(1),(6),(21) will depend on the total effect of interlaminar stresses on longitudinal displacement. In the present analysis, α is found only in the expression of shear-lag constant, so, $\alpha=2$ was shown in [6, 9, 17], $\alpha=0$ was shown in [7, 10, 13]. We adopt $\alpha = 1.1$ and give good prediction with a lot of experimental results for the $[0_n/90_m]_S$ CFRP, GFRP, KFRP laminates from Highsmith, A.S.D.Wang, Beaumont and Groves[16].

Figs.4 and 5 show the growth of crack density with the increasing tensile loading. However, the predicted curves don't reflect the three-stage mode of crack growth. Fig.6 checks the validity of eqn(12) and (21). Experimental data were published by V.K.Kinra and S.E.Groves respectively. Fig.7 shows the influence of changing the stacking sequence of cross-ply laminate. The experimental data of T300 / 648, $[0_2/90_3]_S$ specimens are presented also. We find the saturate crack density becomes very high but the final stiffness loss in T300 / 648, $[0/90_3/0]_S$ laminate keeps the same value as that of $[0_2/90_3]_S$ laminate. When final fracture occurs in T300 / 648 $[0_2/90_3]_S$ laminate, eqn(19),(20) give $R_2 \approx 0.66$ $R_1 \approx 0.99$. If FPF refers to the onset of the first transverse crack, $R_2 \approx 0.99$. If the Classic Laminate Theory is used to determine the FPF (corresponding to a crack density)[18], R_2 will be given a middle value for the weakest plies. So the occurrence of the FPF doesn't mean the complete failure of the plies.

For the general laminate with transverse cracks in 90° plies, the longitudinal modulus of the laminate can be derived approximately by means of the ply discount method of the Classic Laminate Theory[17-8].

$$E_x = E_r + (E_x^0 - E_r)R_2 \quad (22)$$

where, E_r is the reduced laminate modulus (when $R_1 = 1, R_2 = 0$) and R_2 is determined by eqn(19).

3.3. Development of Edge Delamination Considering Transverse Crack

The edge delamination in carbon fiber laminate has been studied widely, the energy release rate derived from stiffness relation is used to characterize the edge delamination[19–20]. The stiffness loss caused by transverse cracks in glass fiber laminate shouldn't be neglected compared with in that the carbon fiber laminate, so the growth of edge delaminations taking into account the effect of transverse crack will give the more reasonable mechanism [17, 20–21]. We adopt O'Brien's basic assumptions[19]. By means of the parallel springs model, the stiffness loss in the laminate caused by edge delamination and transverse cracking can be written in a unified form[16]

$$E = \left(E^* - E_x(D) \right) \frac{a}{b} + E_x(D) \quad (23)$$

$$E^* = \sum_{i=1}^m E_i t_i / \sum_{i=1}^m t_i \quad (24)$$

where E^* is the modulus of completely delaminated laminate and a/b is the normalized delamination size[19]. $E_x(D)$ is the stiffness loss caused only by transverse cracks. For the $[\pm (30)_2 / 90 / 90]_s$ laminate, it can be expressed by eqn(22) or other forms[12, 14]. When $a=0$, $E = E_x(D) \neq E_x^0$, corresponding experimental result has been shown in ref.20. If the CFRP laminate contains a few 90° plies, the stiffness loss caused by transverse cracking can be neglected, i.e., $E_x(D) \approx E_x^0$, then, eqn(23) will yield O'Brien's formula[19]. For other materials or laminates, eqn(23) will give more reasonable prediction. The test on edge delamination and transverse cracking in glass-epoxy $[\pm (30)_2 / 90 / 90]_s$ laminate were performed as the same method describing in Chapter 2. The results are shown in Fig.8. O'Brien's formula on stiffness loss gives higher prediction value and present formula gives better one. Hence, the strain energy release rate of edge delamination in ref.19 can be written in a modified form

$$G_d = \frac{\varepsilon^2 t}{2} \left[(E_x(D) - E^*) - (b-a) \frac{dE_x(D)}{dD} \cdot \frac{dD}{da} \right] \quad (25)$$

This equation means only the crack density approaches D_{CDS} can the G_d / ε^2 will be a laminate constant(corresponding to a delamination size.) and the predicted onset of delamination should be included in the effect of transverse crack.

4. TRANSVERSE CRACKING IN CONCRETE PAVEMENT

The transverse crack in asphalt concrete pavement is regarded to be caused by the cyclic temperature according to most common view of points[15, 22–4]. The appearance features of transverse crack have been described in ref.24. Those cracks often stem from those serious defects such as check well or drain well or the edge of pavement. Finite element analysis showed higher tensile stress existed in the edge of pavement[24]. Similar result has been shown in composite laminate[19]. Although not all the transverse cracks can run through the width of pavement, they will form a final regular state giving approximate equivalent crack spacing after several years' service. Because the performance of surface layer is similar to that of subgrade and is quite different from that of base, the two-layer system in pavement analysis will be used to explain the regular transverse cracking state[15]. At low temperature, pavements will contract but they're prevented by base so inter-layer shear stress occurs at the interface. As a result, tensile stress exists in pavement and is possible to induce transverse cracking because of the low tensile strength of concrete. As soon as the transverse cracking forms, an analogous shear-lag region will exist in pavements and result in the final regular crack state by the cyclic temperature or its overload[24].

Consider a plane stress problem on cracked pavement. (Fig.9) The materials are assumed to be isotropic and linear elastic and the displacement continues at the interface. The equilibrium equations for pavements and base are

$$\frac{d\sigma_s}{dx} = \frac{\tau_{s/b}}{a} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial\sigma_{bx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial\tau_b}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (26)$$

The boundary conditions require

$$\sigma_s = \sigma_{bx} = \tau_b = 0, \quad (x=0) \quad \text{and} \quad \tau_{s/b} \rightarrow 0, \quad \sigma_s \rightarrow \sigma_s^0, \quad (x \rightarrow \infty) \quad (27)$$

where subscripts s and b represent variables associated with the pavement and base, $\tau_{s/b}$ is the shear stress at the interface between pavements and base. Introduce a stress function of the base

$$\varphi = (1 - e^{-kx}(kx + 1))(\varphi_1 y^4 - \varphi_2 y^2) + g(x) \quad (28)$$

where k is the shear-lag constant and defined as

$$k = \sqrt{\frac{3G_b(aE_s + bE_b)}{E_b E_s b^2 a}} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2(1+\mu)} \left(\frac{1}{b^2} + \frac{E_b}{abE_s} \right)} \quad \left(G_b = \frac{E_b}{2(1+\mu)} \right) \quad (29)$$

The width of transverse crack in the surface layer W_s can be derived[16]

$$W_s = \frac{6\sigma_s^0}{k} \left(\frac{1}{E_s} - \frac{a}{bE_b} \right) \quad (30)$$

and the tensile stress of pavements in x direction

$$\sigma_s = \sigma_s^0 (1 - e^{-kx}(kx + 1)) \quad (31)$$

The saturate crack spacing L_{CDS} will be given by

$$1 - e^{-kx}(kx + 1) = 1 - \varepsilon, \quad \varepsilon \leq 0.1 \quad (32)$$

where σ_s^0 is the stress in pavement at far position from transverse crack, E_s is the effective modulus of pavements and can be expressed by the rule of mixtures such as eqn(24). The depth of transverse crack in base b is difficult to detect and can be given by eqn(30). Fig.10 gives a crack spacing distribution and the predicted value of a highway serving for several years. More results will be shown in ref.24.

5. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

That transverse cracking occurs in a layer under transverse tension will declare the complete failure of a layer. When the layer is placed in the laminated structure such as composite laminate or concrete pavement, the onset of a transverse crack will be uncertain to cause the complete failure of the laminated structure. Shear stress will occur at the interface because of the different material properties of each layer and form the new cracking state due to the tensile stress resulting from the cumulative effect of shear stress. The initial defects can be simulated by the distribution of microflaws, all of them are possible to form transverse cracks unless catastrophic failure occurs in laminate structure. They may form a final regular cracking state combining the existing of shear-lag region and it doesn't mean the complete failure of a layer. A simulated method on mechanism can be designed to reappear the mentioned process of transverse cracking. This laminate consists of two aluminum alloy sheets and a central epoxy casting with a group of designed distributive microflaws[16]. The fiber breakage in adjacent plies caused by transverse cracking is a further problem, especially whether the first transverse crack will indicate the final fracture position of the laminate during fatigue test. It may reveal the reliability mode of laminate structure. In the analysis of the growth of transverse cracks, probability method will be a more reasonable routine[3, 13]. One feature of the stiffness loss in composite laminate due to transverse cracking is that it depends on the ratio of stiffness components of the lamina, so the study on the edge delamination in GFRP laminate should be included in the modification of transverse crack.

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BIOGRAPHIES

Luo-Yu XU received his B.S.degree in Aircraft Design from Beijing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics in 1987. Then he was recommended as a master's student and research assistant of the Fatigue and Fracture Division (Laboratory) at BUAA as a top undergraduate. He's interested in composites when he built composites model aircraft, so he minored in material science as well as civil engineering. Now he's a Research Engineer in Jinan Composite Structure Research Center of the Aerospace Ministry. Current interests include reliability model of laminate structure, ARALL, damage growth and life prediction.

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Fig.1. Transverse cracks and defects in laminate

Fig.2. Experimental curves for crack growth in T300 / Ag80 laminate

Fig.3. Stress-strain relation of laminate and crack growth

Fig.4. Predicted and experimental crack growth for T300 / 648 $[0_2 / 90_3]_s$ laminate

Fig.5. Predicted and experimental crack growth for T300 / Ag80 $[0 / 90_{\frac{3}{2}}]_s$ laminate

Fig.6. Stiffness loss in AS4 / 3502 $[0_m / 90_n / 0_k]_s$ laminate

Fig.7. The influence of changing layup on stiffness loss and saturate crack density in T300 / 648 laminate

Fig.8. Stiffness loss due to edge delamination and transverse crack in $G / E [\pm (30)_2 / 90_{\frac{3}{2}}]_s$ laminates, - · - · - O'Brien's model — Present model

Fig.9. Typical cracking forms of concrete pavement

Fig.10. Transverse crack distribution and predicted saturate spacing of a highway